

**METHODS OF WORKING WITH GIFTED CHILDREN IN ORGANIZING
EXTRA-CLASS ACTIVITIES**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14406008>

Abstract. *Talent and genius are the highest level of development of human abilities. The article talks about the features of working with gifted children.*

Keywords: *talent, education, nationality, teacher, abilities, child.*

**МЕТОДИКА РАБОТЫ С ОДАРЕННЫМИ ДЕТЬМИ ПРИ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ
ВНЕКЛАСНОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ**

Аннотация. *Талант и гениальность являются высшим уровнем развития способностей человека. В статье говорится об особенностях работы с одаренными детьми.*

Ключевые слова: *талант, образование, национальность, учитель, способности, ребенок.*

In the educational process, special talents and abilities of students are manifested in various aspects of pedagogical activity. Working with gifted children at school, especially in primary grades, effectively organizing educational and upbringing work to reveal their abilities and talents, and developing students' talents are one of the important tasks in our increasingly developing world. In the conditions of modern education, one of the most important qualities and tasks required of today's teachers is to educate the younger generation as well-rounded individuals and knowledgeable, intellectually capable individuals who can compete in science in the world. In particular, in order for gifted children and talented young people to demonstrate their limited knowledge and develop their talents, teachers must feel a sense of responsibility and conscientiously approach the education of young people who are the future of the country.

Nowadays, it is necessary to create the most favorable conditions for intelligent, creative, independent-thinking, highly gifted and talented young people, to direct and manage their activities towards a specific goal. Such young people have a powerful force that can bring the national potential of the people to the level of world requirements in various fields. From this perspective, it is important to approach the problem, find talented young people, and establish their activities.

On a global scale, it is important to improve the system of organizing an in-depth and specialized educational process taking into account the talents, abilities, interests, and levels of academic mastery of students, to create pedagogical foundations for developing independence, creative initiative, and social responsibility in students, to develop educational technologies focused on the student's personality, to diagnose students' talents, and to provide spiritual and moral support.

Also, the selection of talented students and the organization of their educational activities, the upbringing and development of talented students as a priority area of pedagogical activity are one of the pressing issues today. An example of this is the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 3, 2019 No. PD-4306 “On measures to identify talented youth and organize a continuous system of training highly qualified personnel”.

In particular, “In our country, consistent measures are being implemented to support promising youth, realize their talents, and create additional conditions for the effective implementation of scientific research and innovation activities. At the same time, there is a need to identify talented young people and improve the continuous system of training highly qualified personnel in order to increase the desire and intellectual potential of the growing younger generation to acquire knowledge, as well as to further enhance the prestige of our country in the international arena.

A student's unique strong ability to acquire knowledge, his desire and perseverance for knowledge are called academic talent. The ability to analyze, think, and compare facts is called intellectual talent.

First of all, gifted children must be able to be identified. Identifying gifted children is not a one-time event, but a long-term process. It should begin in primary school based on observation, study of psychological characteristics, speech, memory, logical thinking. Gifted children have a number of features: they are inquisitive, persistent in searching for answers, often ask deep questions, are inclined to think, and have a good memory.

The following types of activities are used in the lessons

Use of modern educational technologies and methods:

- developmental and problem-based learning technologies,
- critical thinking technology,
- information and communication technologies,
- health-preserving technologies,
- technology of differentiated and individual approach to each child;

- activity method,
- project and research activities of students;

Work of "consultants" in the lesson (motivated students in a certain educational area supervise the rest, implementing mutual training and assistance to the teacher in the educational process);

Possibility of choosing tasks of increased complexity during the performance of tests, checks and independent work on various subjects;

Offering students individual homework of an advanced level, creative and search nature (their own initiative is welcomed).

For this category of children, the following methods of work are preferable:

- research;
- partial search;
- problem; Forms of work:
 - class - lesson (work in pairs, in small groups), multi-level tasks, creative tasks;
 - consultation on the problem that has arisen;
 - discussion;
 - games.

Taking into account the psychological characteristics of gifted children, the following methods and techniques of work are used in lessons:

problem dialogue,

press conference

The "Press Conference" technique is based on children's ability to ask questions of a substantive nature. Moreover, questions can be reproductive (to repeat knowledge), expanding (to learn something new about the subject) and developing (carrying a research basis)

A gifted child in a family is the pride of the family. In many cases, a child's talent may go unnoticed in a family. If the child is the firstborn in the family or all the children are talented, this can be considered normal in the family.

However, not all parents are proud of such children. They do not want their child to stand out from others. It would be appropriate if parents noticed the talent in their children in time and helped them in every way. In some cases, talented children are tormented in the family. The child may not be able to cope with this, and on the contrary, the parents of a child without talent and incompetence demand a lot from him, such a process can undermine the child's health.

It is possible to restore health, but it is much more difficult to eliminate the moral damage caused. If there is talent, it is good to help him in time, but "creating" talent is an insult to the child.

Parents often express their child's talent by the child's early speech development, early learning to count, sharpness of memory and curiosity. Such children are also characterized by imagination and speed of thinking, in some cases such features are not clearly manifested. An important task of parents is to monitor and notice the comprehensive development of such a child.

More precisely, they should notice such children in a timely manner, identify their talent and help them develop. It is impossible for a family not only to identify a gifted child, but also to show a special attitude to such a child, because this can lead to other negative (conflictual) situations, that is, to the emergence of prejudice and relationships between other children in the family. In this case, the activities of a social pedagogue working at school will be effective.

To do this, first of all, the social pedagogue should not forget about the importance of educating a child, regardless of his or her level of talent. He or she (the gifted child) should be taught patience, contentment, hard work, and independent decision-making.

The pedagogue-teacher must properly organize his or her attitude towards a gifted child, only then can he or she find the right way to interact with him or her.

Extracurricular activities in working with gifted children include:

- ✓ Extracurricular work on academic subjects (weeks and decades);
- ✓ Exhibitions of students' creative works;
- ✓ Participation in school, district subject Olympiads, marathons and competitions
- ✓ Participation in the work of the scientific society of younger students
- ✓ Project and research activities;
- ✓ Participation in the district review of students' achievements;
- ✓ District, regional sports competitions, marathons, competitions

Every child is talented in his own way. Identifying and raising gifted, talented children is certainly an important issue. Our task is to structure educational and extracurricular activities, educational work so that any individual characteristics of children, containing the seeds of advanced development in one area or another, are noticed, developed and realized in our pedagogical activities with these children.

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